

Age <= 65 | Sex: Female

Age <= 65 | Sex: Male

Age > 65 | Sex: Female

Age > 65 | Sex: Male

of Hemorrhagic Strokes per 1000 AF diagnoses

Proportion of patients under DOACs treatment

Year